

Consciousness of Objects Alters Only Their Perception Over Time

Aman Chawla

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Abstract

There is an interpretation problem in quantum mechanics. Does the wave function represent a real “thing?” Does it “really” collapse when measured? In this work the authors present an analysis of perception at the nano or quantum level.

To measure an object one has to enter its milieu or proximity. Since metric perturbations are long wavelength entities, two things - the object and the experimentalist or observer can easily be in the same milieu and see an almost identical environment of metric waves.

Given this identical background, the object need not be affected by the metric perturbations if it is non-massive. However, within the observer there may be a change in the perception of the object. Suppose two axon tracts with nearby nodes start off with two entangled ions. As the metric perturbation g_1 arrives at axon 1 to influence ion 1 via V_1 , it performs a quantum gate Q_1 on the motional state of the ion, details of which were provided in a previous preprint. This alters the quantum state of ion 1 and hence that of ion 2. Once the wave reaches ion 2, traveling at c , even if other conditions are unchanged, it will only have access to an altered state of ion 2. Thus the final outcome of the g-wave induced gate on ion 2 will be different from what it would have been had the two axons been influenced simultaneously by the same g-wave. In effect, g_2 has operated on ion 2. In a similar way, all the other operations on ion 2 will be affected and a different overall computation will have occurred than on axon 1's ion. Consequently, the quantum information sent to higher brain regions, about the object, will be different in tract 2 as compared to tract 1. Thus if tract 1 represents an earlier epoch to the brain, and tract 2 is processed as a later epoch, say relative to the g_1 onset, the perception of the external object has undergone a transformation. In other words, consciousness of the object has changed, not the object itself, by coming into its milieu.

This counters the widely held opinion that consciousness somehow alters objects, at least at the quantum level, and is perhaps responsible for the collapse of the wavefunction.